

PROBABILISTIC THERMOELASTIC EFFECTIVE CHARACTERISTICS FOR COMPOSITES WITH INTERFACE DEFECTS

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SUMMARY: The main purpose of the paper is to present the results of probabilistic homogenization of the fiber-reinforced composites with stochastic interface defects. The mathematical model of the composite is based on the interphase containing all interface defects which are averaged within this region. Next, the effective modulus method is applied to compute the effective thermoelastic characteristics of the composite. The probabilistic characteristics of the homogenized material properties tensor are obtained using the Monte-Carlo simulation technique linked with the Finite Element Method based program. Some further developments of the approach presented finishing the paper.

KEYWORDS: Interface problems, probabilistic methods, homogenization, Monte-Carlo simulation

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials play a very important role in nowadays engineering from aerospace technology and nuclear devices to microelectronics or structural engineering applications. Since this fact and taking into account still growing role of numerical FEM or BEM-based experiments in designing of structures and industrial processes, one of the most important purposes of computational mechanics researches is precise modeling of these materials. On the other hand, experimental sciences prove that every structural parameter has a random or, in fact, due to the degradation processes, stochastic character. Thus, many probabilistic approaches have been worked out to simulate more accurately the real behavior of composite materials and structures. The most efficient probabilistic computational techniques are the Monte-Carlo simulation (MCS) method [6,8] and the Stochastic Finite Element Method (SFEM) [7]. Thanks to these tools we are able to analyze the boundary problems with randomly varying coefficients (in space or in time) as well as engineering systems with random uncertainties in macro or microgeometry. All these phenomena appear extensively in the field of composite materials since natural inhomogeneities of the components and due to the fabrication processes causing for example thermal stresses which are crucial for interfaces quality.

Considering above, the paper presented is devoted to the probabilistic computational analysis of homogenization of linear elasticity and heat conduction problems in two-component fiber-reinforced periodic composite materials. The homogenization method [1] based on the effective modules approach [9] is proposed to eliminate the needs of complicated discretization of the whole structure (especially interphase) and enables one to model the real composite with interface defects as homogeneous medium characterized by the thermoelastic random effective parameters. Thanks to the Monte-Carlo simulation technique implemented in the homogenization-oriented FEM-based program it is possible to compute the probabilistic moments or coefficients of any order and, further, without any restrictions on the input random variables coefficients of variation [7].

2. GENERAL COMPOSITE MODEL

Let us consider the cross-section of the fiber-reinforced composite with long fiber, we assume that this section is constant along the fiber direction. The Representative Volume Element (RVE) is defined deterministically as the minimal element of the section that due to some homothety (being deterministic geometric transformation) can be transformed into the whole structure. We introduce the rectangular RVE with embedded centrally circular fiber - the example of such structure is shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1: Periodic composite structure

Fig. 2: Periodicity cell in 3D view

Ω_1 denotes here the fiber region while Ω_2 is the matrix. Let us assume that the constituents of the composite are linear elastic and transversely isotropic and that there is no coupling between the mechanical and thermal effects. Thermoelastic material properties of the composite are defined by the expected values and covariances of Young moduli, Poisson and heat conductivity coefficients of the fiber and matrix as follows:

$$E[\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{y}; \omega)] = \begin{cases} p_1 & ; \mathbf{y} \in \Omega_1 \\ p_2 & ; \mathbf{y} \in \Omega_2 \end{cases} ; \text{Cov}(p_i(\mathbf{y}; \omega); p_j(\mathbf{y}; \omega)) = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Var } p_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \text{Var } p_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The appropriate covariances are equal to 0 due to the lack of the respective experimental data on probabilistic correlation of any material property in different materials; the different material parameters are uncorrelated, too.

Next, we consider structural discontinuities between the fiber and matrix in the form of some random material defects located along the interface into the matrix region. We assume that the maximal defects dimensions are relatively small with the comparison to the fiber radius and the RVE geometrical dimensions.

Fig. 3: Bubble idealization of the interface defect

To derive a mathematical and numerical model for the linear elastostatics and heat conduction problems related to the fiber-reinforced composite with such interface inhomogeneities we assume that:

- 1) there is a finite number of material defects along the RVE interface;
- 2) the defects are approximated by the semi-circles (so-called „bubbles”, see [11]) lying with their diameters along the interface within the matrix region;
- 3) all thermoelastic characteristics specified above are assumed equal to 0 for the bubbles interiors;

To complete the interface model we introduce the total number of defects considered ‘n’ and the radius of the bubbles ‘r’ as next two Gaussian random parameters of the problem. These parameters are defined uniquely, as previously, by their expected values ($E[n]$, $E[r]$) and their variances ($\text{Var}(n)$, $\text{Var}(r)$).

It should be underlined that the model introduced approximate the real defects very precisely, however to build up a numerical procedure the bubbles should be appropriately averaged within the interphase introduced in the matrix region, between the composite constituents. Further, we assume that the interphase has the constant thickness along the fiber and that the thickness is so calculated that all defects are located in this region with probability equal to 1. Thus we can introduce the interphase thickness ‘d’ as:

$$d = E[r] + 3\sqrt{\text{Var}(r)}, \quad (2)$$

what follows Gaussian character of the bubble radius random variable. The bubbles as well as the interphase (with thickness denoted as Δ_{2c}) are presented schematically in Figs. 4 and 5.

Fig. 4: Bubbles around the fiber (RVE quarter)

Fig. 5: Interphase into the matrix

Next, we derive the first two probabilistic moments of the equivalent material properties; to this purpose the probabilistic version of the spatial averaging method is proposed. It is known that any effective property $Y^{(av)}$ characterizing the averaged region Ω can be calculated as:

$$Y^{(av)} = \frac{\sum_{a=1}^n Y_a |\Omega_a|}{|\Omega|}; \quad x \in \Omega, \quad (3)$$

where $|\Omega|$ is the total section area of Ω while the property Y_a is defined within the region Ω_a .

Further, we can derive the closed equations for the expected values and variances of the $Y^{(av)}$ if only Ω is defined deterministically while Y_a, Ω_a for all 'a' are uncorrelated random fields.

Hence, the expected value of probabilistically averaged $Y^{(pav)}(\omega)$ on Ω can be written as:

$$E[Y^{(pav)}(\omega)] = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \sum_{a=1}^n E[Y_a(\omega)] E[|\Omega_a(\omega)|], \quad (4)$$

and, similarly, the variance as

$$\text{Var}(Y^{(pav)}(\omega)) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|^2} \sum_{a=1}^n \text{Var}(Y_a(\omega)) \text{Var}(|\Omega_a(\omega)|). \quad (5)$$

Using these equations we calculate the probabilistic moments of the elasticity tensor components and the heat conductivity for the hypothetical material introduced in the interphase equivalent to matrix and the bubbles introduced in its region. We provide such calculations on the example of interphase Young modulus $e_i^{(eff)}$. We have:

$$E[e_i^{(eff)}] = E\left[\frac{S_{\Omega_i} - S_b}{S_{\Omega_i}} \cdot e_2\right] = E[e_2] \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{S_{\Omega_i}} \cdot E[S_b]\right), \quad (6)$$

where S_b, S_{Ω_i} denote the bubbles and the interphase total areas and where

$$S_{\Omega_i} = \Pi \left\{ \left(R + E[r] + 3\sqrt{\text{Var}[r]} \right)^2 - R^2 \right\}. \quad (7)$$

In a similar way we obtain the variance as:

$$\text{Var}(e_i^{(eff)}) = \text{Var}\left(\left(1 - \frac{S_b}{S_{\Omega_i}}\right) \cdot e_2\right). \quad (8)$$

We can transform the last equation to the following form:

$$\text{Var}(e_i^{(eff)}) = \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{S_{\Omega_i}} E[S_b] \right\}^2 \cdot \text{Var}[e_2] + \frac{1}{S_{\Omega_i}^2} \text{Var}[S_b] \cdot E^2[e_2]. \quad (9)$$

To compute the expected values and variances of the effective Young moduli, the probabilistic parameters of the variable S_b have to be found. As it can be seen

$$S_b = \frac{1}{2} \Pi(r)^2 n. \quad (10)$$

Therefore, we derive from the definition

$$E[S_b] = \frac{\Pi}{2} \cdot E[(r)^2 n] = \frac{\Pi}{2} \cdot \{E^2[r] + \text{Var}[r]\} \cdot E[n] \quad (11)$$

and the variance of S_b

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}[S_b] = & \frac{\Pi^2}{4} (E^2[r] + \text{Var}(r))^2 \cdot \text{Var}(n) + \\ & + \frac{\Pi^2}{2} \text{Var}(r) \cdot (E^2[n] + \text{Var}(n)) \cdot (2E^2[r] + \text{Var}(r)) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

To complete the description of the interphase material properties probabilistic moments we introduce these dependencies into equations (6,8); another interphase parameters (Poisson and heat conductivity coefficient) are calculated by the same way if only the assumption of the zeroing of corresponding parameter is fulfilled for the bubbles interiors.

It should be noted that we can model both structural and interface defects using elliptical shapes as well but as the effect we obtain the next geometrical parameter into the model. By the analogy we can model these defects by the spherical or ellipsoidal shape in 3D analysis. Considering the fact that the bubbles are assumed to be small in comparison with fiber radius we can introduce them into the finite element stiffnesses and treat them as element variables.

Finally, it should be mentioned that original two-component composite with randomly defined interface defects is replaced in our model with the three component one where the third component denotes the interphase introduced between two original materials. All composite constituents are continuous and perfectly bonded with material properties are uniquely defined by their first two probabilistic moments.

3. HOMOGENIZATION EQUATIONS

Next we formulate the probabilistic homogenization problem by the use of the effective modulus method that enables to calculate the effective material parameters. The variational formulations for the linear elastostatic and heat conduction homogenization problems for the two component composites can be written as:

$$\sum_{a=1}^2 \int_{\Omega_a} C_{ijkl}^{(a)} \varepsilon_{kl}(\chi_{(pq)}) \varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{v}) d\Omega = \int_{\partial\Omega_{12}} [C_{ijpq}] n_j v_i d(\partial\Omega), \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{a=1}^2 \int_{\Omega_a} \left[\delta\theta(k_i^{(a)} \Phi_{,i}) \right]_{,i} d\Omega = \int_{\partial\Omega_{12}} \delta\theta [k_i] n_i d(\partial\Omega). \quad (14)$$

It should be noted that in the case of three component media we integrate the L.H.S. over three components and the R.H.S. within two interfaces. Further, we can derive the equations describing effective material parameters however under condition that the scale between the RVE and the whole composite structure tends to 0. We have [6,9]:

$$C_{ijkl}^{(eff)}(\omega) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} \left(C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}; \omega) + C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}; \omega) \varepsilon_{mn}^y(\chi_{(kl)p}(\mathbf{y}; \omega)) \right) d\Omega, \quad (15)$$

$$k^{(eff)}(\omega) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} k(\mathbf{y}; \omega) d\Omega - \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} k(\mathbf{y}; \omega) 1_i \Phi_{,i}(\mathbf{y}; \omega) d\Omega, \quad (16)$$

where χ, Φ denote homogenization functions being computed in the cell problems solved on the RVE. The periodicity conditions on external cell boundaries for homogenization functions are assumed and the difference of constitutive (or heat conductivity) tensor components at the interface is applied. Using equations (15,16) we can estimate using Monte-Carlo simulation technique the expected values, coefficients of variation or higher order probabilistic moments and coefficients of the homogenized parameters as well as their stochastic sensitivity with respect to input material characteristics or fiber volume in the RVE. On the other hand, we can compare these characteristics with the upper and lower bounds for the effective elasticity or conductivity tensor components. These bounds, due to the Voigt-Reuss approach [2], may be calculated for the effective heat conductivity coefficient as:

$$\sup k = \frac{\Omega_1 \cdot k_1 + \Omega_2 \cdot k_2}{\Omega}, \quad (17)$$

$$\inf k = \frac{\Omega \cdot k_1 \cdot k_2}{\Omega_1 \cdot k_2 + \Omega_2 \cdot k_1}, \quad (18)$$

and, analogically to formulations (13) and (14), may be extended on the composites with the total number of components higher than 2. Some theoretical, computational as well as technological comments in this matter can be found in [8] where the 4-component composite is homogenized probabilistically. Starting from the homogenization method presented above we can compute the homogenized material properties tensors for the composites with random geometry as it was done in [4] or to link with some digital-based image processors [10].

4. COMPUTATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

The fiber-reinforced glass-epoxy composite example with the interphase between the fiber and matrix is analyzed in the computational experiments; the microgeometry of the periodicity cell is shown in Fig. 6; the whole analysis is performed by the use of the program MCCEFF [6].

Fig. 6: The RVE of the fiber composite with interphase

The heat conductivity coefficients of the composite constituents are taken as equal to 0.038 for fiber and 0.600 for matrix. Generally, 11 computational experiments are performed to compute effective heat conductivity for the composite considered where heat conductivity of the interphase is increased from 50% of matrix conductivity with increment equal to 10% for each next test. The weaker interphase in our tests may simulate any boundary defects appearing in fiber-reinforced composites that are caused by the difference in thermal stresses during fabrication process in metal matrix composites (MMC) mainly. On the other hand, stronger interphase model is equivalent to the case when some layer between fiber and matrix is introduced to enforce the interface between the components [2].

Table. 1. Effective heat conductivity coefficients for the fiber composite with interphase

k_i	sup k	k	inf k
0,30	0,3196	0,1227	0,0761
0,36	0,3196	0,1240	0,0763
0,42	0,3197	0,1251	0,0764
0,48	0,3197	0,1261	0,0765
0,54	0,3197	0,1270	0,0766
0,60	0,3197	0,1279	0,0767
0,66	0,3197	0,1286	0,0768
0,72	0,3198	0,1293	0,0769
0,78	0,3198	0,1303	0,0770
0,84	0,3198	0,1316	0,0772
0,90	0,3198	0,1324	0,0773

Studying the results collected in Tab. 1, we can observe some sensitivity of the effective heat conductivity coefficient for the whole composite with respect to the coefficient characterizing the interphase. It should be mentioned that analogical results can be noticed analyzing the effective elasticity tensor components - some differences between particular components are observed. It is visible that the homogenization method presented confirms the crucial role of the interphase on the overall characteristics of the composite structure.

Next computational experiments are devoted to homogenization of the effective elasticity tensor components for the composites with stochastic interface defects. The elastic parameters are taken as: $E[e_1]=84.0$ GPa, $E[\nu_1]=0.22$ for the fiber and $E[e_2]=4.0$ GPa, $E[\nu_2]=0.34$ for the matrix. Considering a great number of parameters in the model it was necessary to analyze the stochastic sensitivity of effective elasticity tensor components; it is done with respect to the expected values of interface defects number and radii. The following input values are taken: $E[r]=3\%*R$ (MSM), $E[r]=4\%*R$ (SSM) and $E[r]=5\%*R$ (DSM); The expectation of defects total number $E[n]$ is taken to be equivalent to debonded part of an interface (from 10% to 60% every 5%).

Fig. 7: Expected values of the component $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)$

Fig. 8: The coefficients of variation of the component $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)$

Probabilistic moments of the effective elasticity tensor obtained as a result of the simulations are collected in Figs 7 and 8: the expected values of $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)$ are marked on the vertical axis of Fig. 7 while the coefficients of variation - on the respective axis of the next figure. The ratio of interface discontinuities to the whole boundary is marked on the horizontal axes of these figures.

The decrease of the expected values computed with the increase of the interface defects number is observed with generally small differences in comparison with the composite without these discontinuities, what agrees with an engineering intuition very well. For the increase of the parameter DB from 10% to 60% the decrease considered is about 10% for $E[C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)]$. Moreover, it can be seen that for an increase of the expected values of the interface defects the values of $E[C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)]$ decreases and, at the same time, a decrease in differences between $E[C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega)]$ for different defects radii are noticed. Taking into account the coefficients of variation, quite reverse observations can be done. These coefficients increase nonlinearly together with the parameter DB increase in all tests. This dependence has a character similar to the behavior of coefficient of variation of the Young modulus obtained during the interphase probabilistic averaging [7]. Further, the correlation of interface defects value increase and $\alpha(C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega))$ increase is observed and, at the same time, all results are in the range of coefficients of variation of the composite components elastic characteristics.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

1. The approach presented of probabilistic effective modeling of random composite materials may be successfully implemented in any commercial Finite Element Method package (the programs ABAQUS, ANSYS or MARC, for instance) as well as the Boundary Element Method [5] code (cf. the system BEASY). The computer implementation may be provided by the use of Monte-Carlo simulation (MCS) technique as well as, alternatively, using the Stochastic Finite Element Method (SFEM) methodology, however the first one seems to be the most recommended.
2. The results of the computational analyses presented in the paper confirm that the interphase between the constituents of the fiber-reinforced composite influence significantly its overall behavior and, as the effect, effective thermoelastic characteristics and their first two probabilistic moments. The probabilistic uncertainty measure for the composite effective behavior increase together with an increase of the number and radii of the interface defects parameters, what agrees with engineering intuition in this matter. Further sensitivity studies, deterministic as well as stochastic, are recommended to verify the most crucial parameters group of the composite model improved and, to compare with the other approaches in this field.
3. Finally, it should be mentioned that the approach proposed will enable in further developments to carry out the computational analysis of stochastic coupled thermomechanical or another coupled processes or fields in composite materials as well as to formulate the appropriate stochastic reliability conditions on composites engineering applications. The homogenization of heat conduction problem in its probabilistic version may be used to calculate probabilistic moments of the effective characteristics for the whole class of linear potential field problems, for instance.

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